

G-CONTROL FATIGUE CHARACTERIZATION OF SANDWICH COMPOSITES WITH FOAM CORE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents experimental results from cyclic crack propagation tests performed on sandwich specimens with glass/epoxy face sheets and PVC foam cores using the G-controlled cyclic energy release rate (ΔG) test procedure. Finite element analysis was used to determine the mode-mixity of the crack loading while compliance and energy release rate were determined using an analytical model. Experimental crack growth cyclic tests were carried out on pre-cracked MMB sandwich specimens with H45, H100 and H160 PVC foam cores under mode I loading conditions. Crack propagation diagrams showing da/dN vs ΔG curves were obtained to establish the Paris-Erdogan relation for each material combination tested. Results showed constant crack growth rates for all the materials tested and revealed the influence on crack propagation speed of foam density (the higher the foam density, the slower the crack propagation).

1 INTRODUCTION

Many studies on fatigue crack propagation in sandwich materials are available in the literature. Shippa et al [1] used the DCB and CSB methods to characterize foam core sandwich specimens under mode I and mode II conditions. Olurin et al. [2] performed cyclic debond growth studies in sandwich CT specimens with aluminium foam core. Gillespie et al [3] determined da/dN for fatigue crack growth at the face-core interface in sandwich specimens with ceramic tiles core. Saenz et al [4] tested sandwich specimens with PVC and PES foam cores using the DCB method.

All the above mentioned studies are based on load or displacement controlled testing approaches, which lead to increasing or decreasing energy release rate at the crack tip as the crack grows. Manca et al. [5] developed a testing methodology called G-control which maintains a constant level of ΔG at the crack tip as the debond propagates. Such technique employs analytical and finite element models to determine the compliance, energy release rate and mode mixity at the crack tip.

The work described in this paper presents a new approach of face/core interface crack growth characterization of sandwich MMB specimens with various PVC foam cores (H45, H100 and H160) using the G-control technique. Prior to the MMB tests, both in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical properties such as Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of the face sheets were determined and used in the FE and analytical simulations of the cracked sandwich specimen. Fatigue crack propagation tests were performed under mode I and mode II dominant conditions over a range of constant ΔG levels and da/dN versus ΔG curves were constructed and examined.

2 MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

MMB sandwich specimens with quasi-isotropic GFRP face sheets and 3 types of PVC foam core (H45, H100 and H160) were tested. The face material was characterized by several mechanical tests (tensile, compression and shear tests) to determine in-plane and out-of-plane mechanical properties, such as Young's modulus, Poisson ratio and shear modulus. The properties of core materials were provided by the manufacturer. The mechanical properties of face and core were then input to finite element and analytical models of the sandwich specimen to determine mode-mixity and energy release rate.

Crack propagation tests were performed using the MMB test rig (Fig. 1). The test rig consists of a base, a loading lever and a loading yoke and allows a wide range of mixed mode crack loading by adjusting the lever arm length.

Figure 1: MMB specimen and test rig

This method was adopted as international ASTM standard in 2006 [6] and, although such standard includes only static testing of monolithic unidirectional fiber reinforced polymeric composites, it has also been widely used for many years in fatigue testing of composite materials [7,8], and extended to cyclic crack propagation studies of sandwich specimens [9,10].

Sandwich MMB specimens were designed and manufactured according to recommendations indicated in [6] and piano hinges were adhesively fixed to the specimen following the instructions in [11] using epoxy glue Araldite 2015. Specimens were 250 mm long and 35 mm wide and were manufactured with 2 mm thick GFRP face sheets and foam cores of 10 and 20 mm thickness.

The G-control method is a compliance-based fatigue testing technique for controlled cyclic crack growth characterization at constant ΔG [5]. This method requires monitoring of the compliance at each cycle of the fatigue crack propagation test, as schematically described in the diagram in Fig. 2. A desired ΔG_d level and R -ratio are first selected, and a pre-defined “ n ” number of displacement controlled cycles is run, while the compliance is monitored. Calculation of the crack length and measurement of the maximum and minimum loads, P_{max} and P_{min} , allows calculation of ΔG . If the actual ΔG range is different from the targeted, the maximum and minimum opening displacements are adjusted by a small increment p and another “ n ” cycles are executed; if on the other hand ΔG is equal to the desired level, an additional “ n ” cycles are executed at the same maximum and minimum displacements. Such sequence of operations is repeated in a loop, allowing the crack to grow at constant ΔG and, consequently, at constant speed.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the G-control method.

A 2D plain strain finite element model of the MMB sandwich specimen was built using the commercial code ANSYS and used to determine the mode mixity angle at the crack tip. The specimen was modeled using 4 and 8 nodes iso-parametric elements and a very fine mesh was used around the crack tip in order to obtain accurate results. The foam core material was considered to behave isotropic, while the face sheets were modeled as orthotropic. The mode mixity phase angle ψ_R (reduced formulation) was calculated using the CSDE method (Crack Surface Displacement Extrapolation) [12].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section results from the cyclic crack propagation tests of three sandwich materials are presented. For each core material, specimens were tested under mode I dominant loading conditions. Results for crack propagation are represented in log-log plots showing cyclic energy release rate ΔG on the x-axis and crack growth speed da/dN on the y-axis. For each of the plots a least-squares regression line was derived, based on the modified Paris-Erdogan relation [13]

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta G)^m \quad (1)$$

where C and m are characteristic parameters determined from curve fitting.

Plots summarizing the crack propagation curves for the foams tested under mode I dominant loading conditions are presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 3: da/dN vs ΔG results for mode I dominated growth in sandwich specimens with GFRP face and H45, H100 and H160 foam cores ($\Psi_R = -2^\circ$).

Although the exponent m is very similar among all of the tested materials, a clear-cut difference can be seen between H45 cored sandwich specimens, which exhibited crack propagation starting from $\Delta G = 80 \text{ J/m}^2$, and the sandwich specimens with H100 and H160 foam cores, which required higher energy release rate levels for crack propagation. Such similarity could be explained with the similar cells size of these two foams: the average cell diameter for H100 is about 0.4 mm and H160 cells are about 0.3 mm, while H45 cells are considerably larger (about 0.7 mm).

4 CONCLUSIONS

The G-control testing method was applied to characterize fatigue crack growth in sandwich specimens with GFRP face sheets and H45, H100 and H160 foam cores tested under mode I dominant loading conditions. The G-control methodology allows crack growth material characterization using relatively small number of specimens and avoiding the continuous change in ΔG usually experienced with displacement or load controlled tests, which might be detrimental for crack growth material evaluation especially at high propagation rates. Cyclic tests were performed using the Mixed Mode Bending test rig and specimen, and a compliance-based technique was used to determine crack length and cyclic energy release rate in real time. For all the specimens tested under mode I loading conditions the power law exponent was $m \approx 5$. An overall comparison of the three sandwich materials highlighted similar crack growth rates for H100 and H160, explained by the similar cellular size of the two foam cores. Test results revealed that crack growth rates compared at the same cyclic energy release rate increase with decreasing foam density.

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